

Integrated Industrial Marketing Strategy in Social Media to Increase Electrical Products Awareness for PT Unindo Hi-tech Pratama

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ABSTRACT: In this era of information, it requires everyone to have a marketing knowledge. Marketing knowledge can be implemented for every businesses in all over the world. In B2B business, there is a term of industrial marketing strategy which is a similar marketing strategy, but can be implemented for a long-term relationship with the customers. PT. Unindo Hi-tech Pratama is one of Hiwin distributor in Indonesia which provide mechanical and electrical spare parts for industrial automation needs. The purpose of this study is to find out the reasons for the lack of awareness of the Hiwin electrical products in PT. Unindo Hi-tech Pratama. The research method uses qualitative methods. Qualitative methods are used to obtain primary data and make observations from interviews with owners, employees, and customers. The collected data is then used to create internal and external analysis. Internal analysis is used to gather information about PT. Unindo Hi-tech Pratama internal conditions with VRIO analysis and marketing mix, while external analysis is used to evaluate the industry environment as well as define the behaviour of customers of the company. Furthermore, after external and internal analysis was conducted, the researchers used root cause and produced the cause of the problem on the lack of effective promotions and limited resources in raising awareness of Hiwin electrical products. Based on the analysis, researchers presented a new industrial marketing strategy by maximizing digital marketing and improve marketing division management in order to increase awareness of Hiwin electrical products.

KEYWORDS: Customer behaviour, Digital marketing, Electrical parts, Industrial marketing strategy, VRIO analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

In this information era, marketing is one of the key important things to develop many businesses all over the world. Industrial marketing strategy is a set of strategy to develop the company's customer journey in terms of B2B industrial sector. Marketing strategy has been an important role in company's supply chain to deliver the product's knowledge for potential customers. sales and marketing must integrate well to give guarantee that customer know about the product's main functions and advantages for their businesses. [2] Given the significance of the supply chain to the business, PT Unindo has not yet built a strong marketing plan, particularly for electrical products. Because of this, the business needs an integrated industrial marketing strategy to raise customer awareness of its products. Some social media channels can be utilized by B2B companies to enhance their industrial marketing strategy. In order to raise product awareness and have a significant impact on the business, particularly to increase customer demand for the items, this research will demonstrate how integrated industrial marketing strategy may be used in social media.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

VRIO analysis framework is implied in the resource-based model, which identifies particular types of resources as critical to improved company performance. There are two types of resources: tangible and intangible. [6] The marketing mix is a collection of controllable tactical marketing instruments that a firm use to generate the appropriate analysis of the target market.. All of the things a company can do to affect demand for its products are included in the marketing mix. These options can be divided into four categories, known as the "four Ps": product, pricing, location or place, and promotion. [3] Making use of customer analysis is essential for identifying and understanding the customer's point of view. It is necessary for a company that intends to develop a business plan to first appreciate the perspective of its clients in order to examine the corporation's business strategy. Competitor Analysis focuses on each company against which a firm competes directly. Indeed, intense rivalry creates a strong need to understand competitors [1]. SWOT Analysis is the overall evaluation of a company's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats. It's a way of monitoring the external and internal marketing environment. [4] Business-to-Business marketing, business marketing, and organizational marketing are all terms that can be used to describe industrial marketing. Marketing products and services to businesses is known as industrial marketing or business marketing. [5]

3. METHODOLOGY

Methods used in this research is qualitative approaches. In order to gain a deeper insight of the company's business activities, the qualitative research method collects interpretations. The data comes from primary and secondary sources. The primary data came from an in-depth interview with the owner of the company, the operational manager, and the sales team, as well as conducted questionnaire from company's loyal customers. Secondary data is gathered through internal company data, publications, articles, websites and other media. All of the data will be analysed using SWOT and Root Cause Analysis. The analysis results for each framework will be compiled. The strategy will be developed using Industrial Marketing Strategy and 5A's customer path.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. SWOT

1) Internal Analysis: Strength and Weakness

Based on the internal analysis, the following strengths and weaknesses will be discussed: a)

Strengths of PT Unindo Hi-tech Pratama

- In the company, there is a sales territory management. This management divided into two areas which are west and east area. Those two areas will make the sales team more focus and concentrate with its own area in terms of selling Hiwin products.
- PT. Unindo Hi-tech Pratama is only focusing its product in one brand which is Hiwin from Taiwan. This "one product brand" strategy will make the company more focus to develop Hiwin product in Indonesia and this strategy also make the company won't be distracted with other product brand.
- The sales department in the company always maintain the relationship and the communication with the customers. Also, the management in the company always maintain a good communication with the principal in Taiwan. The company believe that they must serve all of the customers well to achieve customers satisfaction as well as build a good relationship with principal in Taiwan as the company's support system to develop Hiwin brand in Indonesia.
- PT. Unindo has been fully supported by Hiwin principal in Taiwan. It can be shown from principal trust with PT. Unindo to be the co-host of international exhibition in Indonesia.
- The company has a good cashflow, each payment is in accordance with the term of payment. Beside of that, the company also hasn't had bank debt.
- PT. Unindo Hi-tech Pratama has branch office in Cikarang to make the delivery or distribution system of Hiwin products closer to the customers. Thus, the distribution system is no longer through logistics center in Kalideres. Also, the company has a showcase in LTC Glodok, so when customer want to buy Hiwin products when they are in Glodok area, they can visit company showcase and purchase directly right there.

b) Weaknesses of PT Unindo Hi-tech Pratama

- The marketing strategy in PT. Unindo has been developed with regular sales visit to the customers. However, it hasn't strong enough yet, especially for online industrial marketing strategy. In this information era, the company hasn't developed the social media strategy for industrial marketing yet in order to increase brand awareness of company's products.
- Recently, the company sales are strong in Banten, Jakarta, and West Java. Hence, for sales outside those three regions, the company make sales via e-mail and phone call.
- Currently, the company has already had one electrical team. These electrical team hasn't solid yet. However, the company hasn't established integrated robotic division to support the electrical team yet.

2) External Anslsysis: Opportunities and Threats

Based on the external analysis, the following opportunities and threats will be discussed: a)

Opportunities of PT Unindo Hi-tech Pratama

- Company's competitors have a long delivery time, due to low stock of Hiwin products. In the other hand, PT. Unindo has full stock of Hiwin products which will impact to shorter in delivery time.

- Due to most of the customers still rely on customer visit, PT. Unindo's can strengthen its marketing strategy in terms of customer visit by improving the standard operational procedure, etc.
- Because of small amount of social media marketing, it can be an opportunity for PT. Unindo in order to improve social media marketing strategy by entering promotion via social media such as Facebook, LinkedIn, etc. *b) Threats of PT Unindo Hi-tech Pratama*
- PT. Unindo hasn't developed robotic division yet. However, the company's competitors have already done it. Thus, these strong robotic division will make the competitor stronger in terms of provide the customer needs to build an integrated automation system.
- PT. Unindo has been focused in Hiwin product only. In the other hand, company's competitors have been sold other supported automation products from other brands. Thus, it can make them to providing more competitive price for the customer with bundling package of its integrated automations system.

B. Industrial Marketing Strategy

In terms of B2B Marketing, PT Unindo Hi-tech Pratama has mapping out the target market area/sector for each sales supervisor in the company. Joe Sullivan [7] explained about 7 core elements of industrial marketing strategy, which are positioning, website foundation, technology stack, content strategy, lead generation, pipeline management and data analysis. In terms of social media marketing, the company will implementing content strategy marketing which consists of video marketing, social media pages, and social media ads via Facebook and LinkedIn platform.

C. Proposed 5A's Customer Path (Promotion)

1) Aware

At this stage, customers are passively exposed to a wide range of businesses through past interactions, marketing messages, and/or referrals from others. The entire customer journey can be accessed through it. In order to maximize the aware stage, PT. Unindo has obtained it via word of mouth. Furthermore, the company must implement the paid advertisements through social media and online marketplace. Paid advertisements can be implemented via B2B social media such as Facebook and LinkedIn. Activation of Facebook advertisements can be conducted through a paid partnership strategy. The business can create its Facebook company pages for no cost. The company must then set aside some credits when Facebook Ads are enabled if it wants to reach a large audience on Facebook. One of the best B2B channels today for promoting numerous businesses is LinkedIn. PT. Unindo may consider using LinkedIn ads to carry out its advertising budget. The business can experiment with Sponsored Content Ads to increase the reach of its LinkedIn ads. Sponsored content ads are posts on LinkedIn page that can promote on the network.

2) Appeal

At this stage, a potential customer is really interested in what a brand or business has to offer and has a solid comprehension of it. Additionally, during this phase, prospective buyers develop short-term memories or reinforce longterm memories and develop an interest in just a few select brands. In this stage, PT. Unindo can implementing content strategy marketing. Content strategy marketing is a marketing method to appeal customer awareness through photo, video, etc. Thus, in order to maximize this stage, PT. Unindo can create a content such as a photo of all of its products, especially for electrical products. Beside of that, the company also can promoting video about the introduction about the company profile as well as the application of the electrical products in automation industry. The company must strengthen the sales team too. The sales team must be trained how to handle potential customers, how to do presentation in front of potential customers, as well as improve their product knowledge about Hiwin, especially for electrical products.

3) Ask

Ask is a stage when driven from their curiosity, customers actively seek more information from friends and family, the media, and/or directly from brands. In this stage customers also start to compare the price and contact the service center. In order to encourage the desire of potential customers to contact and inquire further about the Hiwin electrical product with company representatives, the company might at this point include the phone number, warehouse address, as well as company's website inside the social media homepage. When a customer wants to compare the firm's pricing to that of its

rivals, the company can also provide a competitive price. In addition, the business can provide variety of products to complement the desired product.

4) Act

Act is the stage when customers decide to buy a particular brand and interact more deeply through the buying and use process. In this stage, the customer feels the experience to buy the product for the first time and also give feedback when there is a problem with the product. The company can include a phone number, WhatsApp number, or website button as part of its social media marketing plan on platforms like LinkedIn or Facebook so that customers can contact the company's representatives quickly and simply. Additionally, the business can use WhatsApp Business, which makes it simpler to manage B2B customers via the WhatsApp app. In terms of B2B messaging, the company can use direct email messaging through Google Mail or Yahoo Mail in order to maintain customer purchases through WhatsApp if it wants to stay in touch with and generate leads from customers, particularly the purchasing department in potential customers' businesses. The business can also hold an after-sales training session for electrical products in order to preserve strong client relations. Customers can learn how to properly program Hiwin electrical devices from the company's electrical specialists.

5) Advocate

Advocate is the last stage of 5A's Kotler Customer Journey. In this stage, the customer will be more loyal with their retention and becomes an advocate for the company because of their purchasing experience. In this stage, PT. Unindo can maintain the loyalty in the long-term relationship by re-call the customers by phone, social media messaging, or email messaging to ask whether there is a product to be requested. Beside of that, for loyal customers, the company also can maintain the stocks by keeping the buffer stock ready. Buffer stock is a stock that has been kept by the company for loyal customers when they want to buy it again in a period of time.

D. Proposed Marketing Competencies

Marketing competency is the actual knowledge and abilities that are specifically reflected in the abilities, performance, and performance that are the responsibility of the marketing function. These competencies support the achievement of a sustainable competitive advantage and are difficult for rivals to copy. Human resources department have an important role in helping company have a good quality of human resources and also to help the company have a good competency, including marketing competency, so that companies are able to achieve their business goals better. There are four possibilities that PT. Unindo should do in improving ads performance based on human resources. The four possibilities are:

1) Create Marketing Division

The first thing that the company must concern is to create the marketing division. This marketing division is separate with sales division. Marketing division is more concern on how to promote and how to increase the potential sales from customers. The purpose of marketing is to effectively communicate about its brand, company, and products. The main goal is to think broadly and concisely in order to describe how the product or service benefits the broadest audience possible, hence generating potential leads.

2) Hire a Marketing Division Manager

After create the marketing division, the next step is to hire a Marketing Division Manager. There are several responsibilities of Marketing Division Manager. Marketing Division Manager have responsibilities to lead the initiation of product promotion, coordinate marketing strategy, set budget for each campaign/advertisement, monitor company growth, as well as try out new marketing processes.

3) Build a solid Marketing Division

After the marketing division has been created and Marketing Division Manager has been hired, PT. Unindo need to build a strong collaboration between Marketing Division and Sales Division in order to create a solid Marketing Division. Solid Marketing Division can help the company to improve its marketing strategy goals. Those strong collaboration can be achieved with 3 knowledge which are product knowledge, customer knowledge and sales knowledge.

4) Create Knowledge Management System for Marketing Division

Knowledge management is the process of boosting business performance through the design and application of tools, processes, and cultures to enhance knowledge production, sharing, and utilization. In order to create a proper knowledge

management system in the company, PT. Unindo can provide the employees with seminar or webinar monthly. Beside of that, routine meetings also needed for marketing division in order to share knowledge with each other.

5) Opening Technical Support Center in Indonesia

Technical Support Center is a group of employee that have a good knowledge to supports Hiwin mechanical and electrical in technical way. Thus, this technical support center would be needed in order to increase the trust for potential customer in Indonesia in terms of technically supports system.

4. CONCLUSION

The fundamental cause is in promotion and human resources, according to marketing views to raise brand recognition of Hiwin electrical products in PT. Unindo. PT. Unindo lacks an effective social media marketing strategy and marketing campaign for promotions. PT. Unindo does not yet have the professional resources and appropriate knowledge management in place to support and optimize marketing strategy on the human resources side in order to raise brand awareness. The researcher provided five recommendations for resolving human resources issues in order to increase brand awareness of Hiwin electrical products in PT. Unindo Hi-tech Pratama, as well as a marketing strategy using 5A's Kotler Customer Journey, in order to address the primary issue based on the root cause of PT. Unindo Hi-tech Pratama.

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